

KICHIK O'LCHAMLI KVAZI-FILIFORM SIMMETRIK LEYBNITS ALGEBRALARINING TASNIFI

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O'zbekiston.

Noassotsiativ algebralar nazariyasi bugungi kunda tez suratlarda o'rganilib kelinayotgan sohalaridan biri bo'lib, Li algebralarining umumlashmasi bo'lgan Leybnits algebralari sinfi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Leybnits algebralari barcha chapdan yoki o'ngdan ko'paytirish operatorlari differentsiallash bo'ladigan algebra sifatida fanga kiritilgan bo'lib, ular mos ravishda chap va o'ng Leybnits algebralari deb nomlanadi. Chap va o'ng Leybnits algebralari simmetrik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lganligi uchun odatda ulardan biri biri o'rganiladi. Bir vaqtning o'zida ham chap ham o'ng Leybnits algebrasi bo'ladigan algebralar esa simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi deb ataladi. Bugungi kunda simmetrik Leybnits algebralarini tasniflashning bir qator usullari mavjud bo'lib, ulardan biri 2014-yilda S.Benayadi va S.Hidri [3] tomonidan taklif qilingan usul hisoblanadi. Bu usul barcha simmetrik Leybnits algebralarini Li algebralari yordamida qurish mumkinligiga asoslanadi. Biz ushbu ishda S.Benayadi va S.Hidri usulidan foydalangan holda ba'zi kichik o'lchamli qvazi-filiform simmetrik Leybnits algebralarining tasnifini keltiramiz.

1-ta'rif: F maydon ustida berilgan $(L, [-, -])$ algebradan olingan ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlar uchun quyidagi ayniyatlar bajarilsa, u holda $(L, [-, -])$ Li algebrasi deyiladi:

$$[x, y] = -[y, x], [x, [y, z]] + [z, [x, y]] + [y, [z, x]] = 0.$$

2-ta'rif: F maydon ustida berilgan $(L, \cdot)$ algebradan olingan ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlar uchun quyidagi ayniyatlar bajarilsa, u holda $(L, \cdot)$ simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi deyiladi:

$$x \cdot (y \cdot z) = (x \cdot y) \cdot z + y \cdot (x \cdot z), (x \cdot y) \cdot z = x \cdot (y \cdot z) + (x \cdot z) \cdot y.$$

Berilgan L simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi uchun quyidagi quyi markaziy qatorni aniqlab olamiz:

$$L^1 = L, L^i = [L^{i-1}, L], i \geq 2.$$

3-ta'rif: Agar n -o'lchamli L simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi uchun

$\dim(L^i) = n - i - 2, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$ shart o‘rinli bo‘lsa, u holda L algebra kvazi-

filiform simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi deyiladi:

Quyida biz kichik o‘lchamli kvazi-filiform Li algebralarining tasnifini keltiramiz [2], [4]:

$$L_{7,3}^1 : \begin{cases} [e_1, e_i] = e_{i+1}, [e_7, e_2] = e_5, [e_7, e_3] = e_6, [e_2, e_4] = e_5, [e_2, e_5] = e_6, 2 \leq i \leq 5. \\ [e_2, e_3] = e_4 + e_7. \end{cases}$$

$$L_{9,5}^1 : \begin{cases} [e_1, e_i] = e_{i+1}, [e_1, e_9] = e_7, [e_2, e_5] = e_9, [e_2, e_6] = 2e_7, [e_2, e_7] = 3e_8, 2 \leq i \leq 5 \\ [e_3, e_4] = -e_9, [e_3, e_5] = -e_7, [e_3, e_9] = -3e_8. \end{cases}$$

$$L_{9,5}^2 : \begin{cases} [e_1, e_i] = e_{i+1}, [e_9, e_2] = 2e_7, [e_9, e_3] = 2e_8, [e_2, e_6] = 2e_7, [e_2, e_7] = e_8, 2 \leq i \leq 7 \\ [e_3, e_5] = -e_7, [e_2, e_5] = e_6 + e_9, [e_4, e_5] = -2e_8. \end{cases}$$

$$L_{9,5}^3 : \begin{cases} [e_1, e_i] = e_{i+1}, [e_1, e_7] = e_8, [e_1, e_9] = e_7, [e_2, e_5] = e_9, [e_2, e_6] = 2e_7, 2 \leq i \leq 5 \\ [e_3, e_4] = -e_9, [e_3, e_5] = -e_7, [e_3, e_6] = 2e_8, [e_4, e_5] = -3e_8. \end{cases}$$

Bizga $(L, \cdot)$ algebra berilgan bo‘lsin. U holda quyidagi ko‘paytmalarni aniqlab olamiz:

$$[x, y] = \frac{1}{2}(x \cdot y - y \cdot x), \quad x \circ y = \frac{1}{2}(x \cdot y + y \cdot x).$$

1-tasdiq. [1] Quyidagi tasdiqlar ekvivalent:

1) $(L, \cdot)$ simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi.

2) Quyidagi shartlar bajariladi:

(a) $(L, [-, -])$ Li algebrasi.

(b) Ixtiyoriy $x, y \in L$ uchun $x \circ y$ ko‘paytma $(L, [-, -])$ algebraning markaziga tegishli bo‘ladi.

(c) Ixtiyoriy $x, y, z \in L$ uchun $([x, y]) \circ z = 0$ va $(x \circ y) \circ z = 0$.

Bu tasdiqdan kelib chiqadiki, $(L, \cdot)$ simmetrik Leybnits algebrasini $(L, [-, -])$ Li algebrasi va ixtiyoriy $(L, [-, -])$ Li algebrasidan olingan x, y, z

elementlar uchun,

$$\omega([x, y], z) = \omega(\omega(x, y), z) = 0$$

tenglikni qanoatlantiruvchi $\omega : L \times L \rightarrow Z(L)$ (bu erda $Z(L)$ Li algebrasining markazi) simmetrik bichikli forma orqali berish mumkin. Ya’ni berilgan Li algebrasi va undagi simmetrik bichikli forma orqali simmetrik Leybnits algebrasining ko‘paytmasi quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$x \cdot y = [x, y] + \omega(x, y).$$

2-tasdiq: $L_{7,3}, L_{9,5}^1, L_{9,5}^2$ va $L_{9,5}^3$ Li algebralari orqali hosil qilingan simmetrik Leybnits algebralari sinfi mos ravishda quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

$$S_{7,3}^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} : \begin{cases} e_1 \cdot e_i = e_{i+1}, e_i \cdot e_1 = -e_{i+1}, e_7 \cdot e_2 = e_5, e_2 \cdot e_7 = -e_5, 3 \leq i \leq 5, \\ e_7 \cdot e_3 = e_6, e_3 \cdot e_7 = -e_6, e_2 \cdot e_4 = e_5, e_4 \cdot e_2 = -e_5, \\ e_2 \cdot e_5 = e_6, e_5 \cdot e_2 = -e_6, e_2 \cdot e_3 = e_4 + e_7, e_3 \cdot e_2 = -e_4 - e_7, \\ e_1 \cdot e_1 = \alpha e_6, e_1 \cdot e_2 = e_3 + \beta e_6, e_2 \cdot e_1 = -e_3 + \beta e_6, e_2 \cdot e_2 = \gamma e_6. \end{cases}$$

$$S_{9,5}^1(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1) : \begin{cases} e_1 \cdot e_i = e_{i+1}, e_i \cdot e_1 = -e_{i+1}, e_1 \cdot e_9 = e_7, e_9 \cdot e_1 = -e_7, 3 \leq i \leq 5, \\ e_2 \cdot e_5 = e_9, e_5 \cdot e_2 = -e_9, e_3 \cdot e_4 = -e_9, e_4 \cdot e_3 = e_9, \\ e_2 \cdot e_6 = 2e_7, e_6 \cdot e_2 = -2e_7, e_2 \cdot e_7 = 3e_8, e_7 \cdot e_2 = -3e_8, \\ e_3 \cdot e_5 = -e_7, e_5 \cdot e_3 = e_7, e_3 \cdot e_9 = -3e_8, e_9 \cdot e_3 = 3e_8, \\ e_1 \cdot e_1 = \alpha_1 e_8, e_1 \cdot e_2 = e_3 + \beta_1 e_8, e_2 \cdot e_1 = -e_3 + \beta_1 e_8, e_2 \cdot e_2 = \gamma_1 e_8. \end{cases}$$

$$S_{9,5}^2(\alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2) : \begin{cases} e_1 \cdot e_i = e_{i+1}, e_i \cdot e_1 = -e_{i+1}, e_2 \cdot e_7 = e_8, e_7 \cdot e_2 = -e_8, 3 \leq i \leq 7, \\ e_3 \cdot e_5 = -e_7, e_5 \cdot e_3 = e_7, e_2 \cdot e_6 = 2e_7, e_6 \cdot e_2 = -2e_7, \\ e_9 \cdot e_2 = 2e_7, e_2 \cdot e_9 = -2e_7, e_9 \cdot e_3 = 2e_8, e_3 \cdot e_9 = -2e_8, \\ e_2 \cdot e_5 = e_6 + e_9, e_5 \cdot e_2 = -e_6 - e_9, e_4 \cdot e_5 = -2e_8, e_5 \cdot e_4 = 2e_8, \\ e_1 \cdot e_1 = \alpha_2 e_8, e_1 \cdot e_2 = e_3 + \beta_2 e_8, e_2 \cdot e_1 = -e_3 + \beta_2 e_8, e_2 \cdot e_2 = \gamma_2 e_8. \end{cases}$$

$$S_{9,5}^3(\alpha_3, \beta_3, \gamma_3) : \begin{cases} e_1 \cdot e_i = e_{i+1}, e_i \cdot e_1 = -e_{i+1}, e_1 \cdot e_7 = e_8, e_7 \cdot e_1 = -e_8, 3 \leq i \leq 7, \\ e_1 \cdot e_9 = e_7, e_9 \cdot e_1 = -e_7, e_3 \cdot e_4 = -e_9, e_4 \cdot e_3 = e_9, \\ e_2 \cdot e_5 = e_9, e_5 \cdot e_2 = -e_9, e_2 \cdot e_6 = 2e_7, e_6 \cdot e_2 = -2e_7, \\ e_3 \cdot e_5 = -e_7, e_5 \cdot e_3 = e_7, e_3 \cdot e_6 = 2e_8, e_6 \cdot e_3 = -2e_8, \\ e_4 \cdot e_5 = -3e_8, e_5 \cdot e_4 = 3e_8, e_1 \cdot e_1 = \alpha_3 e_8, e_2 \cdot e_2 = \gamma_3 e_8, \\ e_1 \cdot e_2 = e_3 + \beta_3 e_8, e_2 \cdot e_1 = -e_3 + \beta_3 e_8. \end{cases}$$

1-teorema: Agar S simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi $L_{7,3}$ orqali hosil qilingan simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi bo‘lsa, u holda u o‘zaro izomorf bo‘lmagan $S_{7,3}^{(1, \beta, \gamma)}, S_{7,3}^{(0,1, \gamma)}, S_{7,3}^{(0,0,1)}$ algebralardan biriga izomorf bo‘ladi.

2-teorema: Agar S simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi $L_{9,5}^1$ orqali hosil qilingan simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi bo‘lsa, u holda u o‘zaro izomorf bo‘lmagan $S_{9,5}^1(\alpha_1, 1, 1), S_{9,5}^1(1, 0, 1), S_{9,5}^1(0, 0, 1), S_{9,5}^1(1, 1, 0), S_{9,5}^1(0, 1, 0), S_{9,5}^1(1, 0, 0)$ algebralardan biriga izomorf bo‘ladi.

3-teorema: Agar S simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi $L_{9,5}^2$ orqali hosil qilingan simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi bo‘lsa, u holda u o‘zaro izomorf bo‘lmagan $S_{9,5}^2(1, \beta_2, \gamma_2), S_{9,5}^2(0, 1, \gamma_2), S_{9,5}^2(0, 0, 1)$ algebralardan biriga izomorf bo‘ladi.

4-teorema: Agar S simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi $L^3_{9,5}$ orqali hosil qilingan simmetrik Leybnits algebrasi bo'lsa, u holda u o'zaro izomorf bo'lmagan $S^3_{9,5}(\alpha_3,1,1), S^3_{9,5}(1,0,1), S^3_{9,5}(0,0,1), S^3_{9,5}(\alpha_3,1,0), S^3_{9,5}(0,1,0), S^3_{9,5}(1,0,0)$ algebralardan biriga izomorf bo'ladi.

REFERENCES

1. Abchir.H., Abid.F., Boucetta.M., A class of Lie racks associated to symmetric Leibniz algebras, Journal of Algebra and Its Applications, 21 (2022) 2250230.
2. Ancochea Bermudez.J.M., Campoamor-Stursberg.R., Garcia Vergnolle.L., Classification of Lie algebras with naturally graded quasi-filiform nilradicals, Journal of Geometry and Physics, 61 (2011) 2168-2186.
3. Benayadi.S., Hidri.S., Quadratic Leibniz algebras, Journal of Lie Theory, 24 (2014) 739-759.
4. Gomez. J.R., Jimenez-Merchan.A., Naturally graded quasi-filiform Lie algebras, Journal of Algebra, 256 (2002) 211-228.